

Enhancement of Reading Comprehension Skills of Newly Appointed Teachers

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Abstract

In English Language Teaching in Myanmar, both teachers and learners try to acquire the four skills using on the updated methods. Among the four skills, according to the researcher's experience, reading seems to be easier than the others to Myanmar learners. But the learners didn't get high marks when they answered the reading comprehension questions which are one fourth of the total marks in most of the exams. This happens to the teachers at the university when they take the English tests like tutorship exam. This research aims to find out whether knowing the reading strategies can enhance the learner to get high marks in reading comprehension questions or not. The participants in this research are 13 newly appointed teachers at Bago University. The subjects were asked to take a pretest (reading comprehension questions). Then they are taught the reading strategies from the book TOEFL Reading Flash by Milada Broukal (2001) by the researcher. After that, they are given the post test again and the marks they got in pretest and posttest are calculated and compared. The results shows that knowing the reading strategies can help the learners to get high marks in reading comprehension questions.

Introduction

In English language teaching and learning in Myanmar, concerning reading skills, though most of the learners seem to acquire this skill more than the other three skills and so do the teachers, the learners don't get high marks in reading as the learners hope. So it quests the researcher why they didn't get high marks in reading comprehension questions and the hypothesis for the researcher is if they know reading strategies, they may get high marks in reading comprehension.

The aim of this research is to find out whether knowing the reading strategies can enhance the teacher learners to get high marks in reading comprehension questions or not. The objectives are to improve the English reading skills of the staff, implement the strategies to encourage the Academic staff, promote the quality of the staff at Bago University and get high marks in the English paper in their promotion Exam for the staff.

What is Reading Comprehension?

Reading is a highly strategic process during which readers are constantly constructing meaning using a variety of strategies, such as activating background knowledge, monitoring and clarifying, making predictions, drawing inferences, asking questions and summarizing. In broad terms, comprehension is the ability of readers to get meaning from text. In what ways comprehension happens is that the readers actively coordinate a number of conscious processes before, during, and after reading (Pressley & Afflerbach, 1995). Good readers are aware of how their reading is going and why. They know, for example, when a text is difficult to read because it contains many new ideas and when it is difficult to read because it is poorly written. They are adept at using their prior knowledge as they read to make predictions about what might happen next and to understand ideas as they encounter them (Paris, Wasik, & Turner, 1991).

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Good readers are often selective, focusing their attention on the parts of the text that are most appropriate to their goals. Effective readers go beyond the literal meaning of text, interpreting what they read by filtering ideas in the text through their prior knowledge. Such interpretations often include an evaluation of the quality of the ideas in the text. Often, such associations are carried out intentionally by thinking about how the ideas in the text seem vaguely familiar and then recalling where similar ideas were presented or encountered. Readers also make predictions and form hypotheses about what will happen next, or what ideas the text will advance. In addition, readers continuously evaluate these predictions and hypotheses and revise them as the reading warrants.

What are Strategies?

Comprehension strategies are conscious or intentional plans that people use in order to achieve a goal (Roit, 2005) and are used deliberately to make sense of text (Afflerbach et al. 2008). Readers use strategies consciously to make sense of the text, remember critical ideas and integrate new learning into existing schema or prior knowledge. Students need to learn how to use strategies independently, to recognize and solve problems, and to delve deeper into text to make connections and inferences.

Strategies are used in combination to solve problems, to think about text and to check understanding. Consequently, teaching comprehension strategies should focus on thinking (Harvey & Goudvis, 2000), problem solving and monitoring understanding. "Being strategic is not a skill that can be taught by drill; it is a method of approaching reading and reading instruction. Much more is required than knowing a strategy; becoming strategic calls for coordinating individual strategies. This coordinating involves altering, adjusting, modifying, testing, and shifting tactics as is fitting, until a reading comprehension problem is solved." (Trabasso and Bouchard, 2002, p. 186) Reading strategically is higher order thinking. It involves transforming information and ideas. For example, summarizing requires evaluating and synthesizing information; making predictions involves combining facts and ideas and making inferences to formulate a type of hypothesis; making connections necessitates making generalizing; and clarifying require identifying problems and developing solutions.

Comprehension strategies are used consciously by the reader to monitor and check understanding, to clarify confusion, and to process text. Strategies are situational and are used intentionally by readers. (McEwan, 2004)

In contrast, once skills are learned, they are used unconsciously, i.e. decoding words or breaking words into syllables. Skills are also the tools readers use to organize the structure of text, e.g., main idea and supporting details, compare and contrast, sequencing, etc.

Seven critical reading strategies to encourage and develop critical reading ability are

1. **Previewing:** Learning about a text before really reading it.
2. **Contextualizing:** Placing a text in its historical, biographical, and cultural contexts.
3. **Questioning to understand and remember:** Asking questions about the content.
4. **Reflecting on challenges to your beliefs and values:** Examining your personal responses.
5. **Outlining and summarizing:** Identifying the main ideas and restating them in your own words.
6. **Evaluating an argument:** Testing the logic of a text as well as its credibility and emotional impact.

7. Comparing and contrasting related readings: Exploring likenesses and differences between texts to understand them better. (<http://www.salisbury.edu>)

According to Broukal (2001), General Strategies for reading are to

- read as widely as possible. Read on as many topics as you can. The more you read the better a reader you will be. You will in this way be exposed to a greater vocabulary.
- read carefully and critically. Ask yourself reading comprehension questions as you are reading.

Strategies for Answering Reading Comprehension Questions are to

- **Read the question first.** Read the question, not the answer choices. When you know the kinds of question you must answer, it will be easier to find the answers.
- **Skim or read the passage quickly.** Do not read word for word or in detail. Read quickly to find the main idea and general organization.
- **Go back to the passage to answer questions.** If you know the answer, you do not need to go back to the passage.
- **Leave the difficult questions until last.**
- **Take a guess when you do not know the answer.** If you do not know the answer, take a guess. When you are taking a guess, first use a process of elimination.
- **Answer all questions.** Never leave any items unanswered. If you have no time left, use your guess letter.

Broukal (2001) mentioned five kinds of reading strategies and these strategies reflect the basic reading skills - reading for details, reading for reference and vocabulary, reading for main ideas, reading for inference and additional reading skills.

Strategies for answering Detail Questions

- The answers to detail questions will follow the order of information presented in the passage.
- The correct answers to detail questions are often a restatement of what is stated in the passage.

If the question has the word NOT or EXCEPT, choose the answer that is not true or not mentioned in the passage. Answers that are true or mentioned in the passage are not correct.

Strategies for answering Reference and Vocabulary Questions

- When answering reference questions be aware that the noun closest to the reference word may not always be the correct answer.
- Reference words may refer to a noun or to a noun phrase made up of several words.
- If you do not know which of the four choices is the correct answer to a reference question, substitute the choices for the reference word.
- If you are unable to answer a vocabulary-in-context question, try to guess the meaning from the context by looking for clues.
- Sometimes the meaning of the word is given near the word in the form of a synonym or paraphrase.
- Sometimes clues are not given but are implied. You can guess the meaning after you have read the whole passage.
- The answer choices for the vocabulary-in-context questions may appear correct because they share the literal meaning of the word, but not the meaning as used in the passage. Look for the meaning as it is used in the passage.

Strategies for answering questions for main ideas

- The main idea is not always the first sentences in the paragraph or passage. It can also appear in the middle or toward the end of a paragraph.
- When the main idea is not clear because each paragraph has a main point, combine all the main points to get the main idea.
- Make sure the answer you select for the main idea question relates to the whole passage and not just to one part of it. You can scan the passage to see whether the main idea you have selected is discussed all through the passage.
- The wrong choices for main idea questions may be one of the following:
 1. True statement that focus on one paragraph or a detail.
 2. Statements that are too general and go beyond the passage.
 3. Statements that are incorrect misinterpretations of the main idea

Strategies for answering inference questions

- Go beyond the information stated in the passage.
- Draw a conclusion or reason out what is implied – that is, what the author of the passage means or believes to be true but has not stated in the passage.
- Remember that the answer to the question will not be stated in the words in the passage.
- Beware of answer choices that go beyond what you can logically infer from the passage. Wrong answer choices will often be too exaggerated or overstated to be precisely correct.

Strategies for additional reading skills

- Questions on drawing a conclusion are similar to inference questions. To answer these questions, remember to draw a conclusion from the information given in the passage. The answer will not be directly stated in the passage.
- Purpose questions are a combination of inference questions and main idea questions asking you why the author wrote the passage. Again, to answer these questions, draw a conclusion from the whole passage to find the author's purpose in writing it.
- Answers to questions about what probably came before the passage or what will probably come after it are not directly stated in the passage. You must draw a conclusion from the information you find. When answering questions about what was discussed preceding, or before, the passage, look at information in the first sentence or the beginning of the passage. When answering questions about what probably comes after the passage, look at the end of the passage, where there may be an indication or transition as to what will come next.
- When answering tone or attitude questions, remember that tone and attitude are implied in a passage and not stated explicitly. When answering tone questions look for words that are neutral, positive, or negative. Most reading passages in this section of the test are neutral in tone. Beware of answer choices that are strong emotional words. Some questions on attitude refer to passages in which the author takes a position for or against a point. In such cases, beware of answer choices that overstate or exaggerate the author's attitude.
- Organization questions ask you about the general organization of the passage or of a particular paragraph.

Research Methods

The subjects in this research are 13 newly appointed teachers (2017) at Bago University. They are three from English Department, two each from Myanmar Department and Botany Department and, one each from Geography Department, Physics Department, Mathematics Department, Zoology Department, Chemistry Department and Geology Department. The research was done in May 2018. They were asked to take a pretest (reading comprehension questions). In this pretest, five reading comprehension exercises, depending on the five reading strategies - reading for details, reading for reference and vocabulary, reading for main ideas, reading for inference and additional reading skills were given. These exercises are taken from the book "TOEFL Reading Flash" by Milada Broukal (2001). At that time, they may or may not have knowledge about reading strategies and they answered the questions after reading the given passages. Their answers were marked and calculated. Then they were taught five reading strategies from "TOEFL Reading Flash" by Milada Broukal (2001) by the researcher 6 hours per week. It lasted four weeks. After that, they were given the post test again which includes the same five reading comprehension exercises. Then their answers were marked and the marks were calculated. The last step was to compare the mark they got in pretest and posttest.

Data Analysis

Table 1: Subjects' marks for pretest and posttest based on reading strategies

Sr No	Name	Reading for detailed information		Reading for reference & vocabulary		Reading for main ideas		Reading for inference		Reading for Additional reading skills	
		pre	post	pre	post	pre	post	pre	post	pre	post
1	S 1	1	1	2	2	3	1	2	2	1	1
2	S 2	1	0.5	3	3	2	3	1	1	3	3
3	S 3	0.5	1	2	3	1	1	2	4	0	2
4	S 4	1.5	1	3	4	3	3	2	4	2	3
5	S 5	0.5	1	4	4	2	3	3	1	1	2
6	S 6	1	1	1	5	0	1	1	1	2	4
7	S 7	0	0.5	3	0	1	1	3	3	1	1
8	S 8	1	1	4	3	3	2	1	1	2	5
9	S 9	1	1	0	3	1	1	2	4	3	2
10	S 10	1	1.5	1	2	2	3	3	3	2	3
11	S 11	1.5	1.5	5	4	2	2	1	1	4	4
12	S 12	1.5	1.5	5	4	1	1	1	2	4	4
13	S 13	1.5	1.5	5	4	1	1	0	2	5	4
		13	14	38	41	22	23	22	29	30	38

In this table, the 13 subjects' marks for pretest and posttest are mentioned and compared. The subjects were marked as S1, S2, etc instead of their names and departments.

Findings and Discussion

As mentioned in the table in data analysis, all the marks for all strategies in the posttest are higher than the pretest in the table. Among all these five kinds of strategies, the marks for strategies for reading for inference and for additional reading skills are the highest (8 marks difference) and the marks for strategies for detailed information and for main ideas are the lowest (1 mark difference). According to the marks compared, the results show that knowing strategies can help the teacher learners to get high marks in reading comprehension.

Conclusion

Based on their experience, the subjects also answered the questionnaire. According to the answers in the questionnaire, in the pretest, they didn't know the reading strategies and they answered the questions by looking for the same words in the paragraph and the questions and choosing the answers although they didn't know how to find the answers and they didn't understand the paragraphs. After knowing the strategies, they came to know how to find the answers in the paragraphs although they didn't understand the given passages. All participants are energetic and hardworking. They want to improve their reading skills, to get high marks in their exam and to get promoted and to realize that the career life is very competitive.

In this research, the aim and objectives of the project are fulfilled; the newly appointed teachers improve their English reading skills, they will get high marks in the English paper in their promotion exam for the staff, this research implemented the strategies to encourage the Academic staff and promote the quality of the staff at Bago University. But in this research paper, reading strategies are just paid attention and other skills of the subjects are neglected but other researches on participants skills like – vocabulary, grammar etc should be done.

In conclusion, the results in this research show that knowing the reading strategies can enhance the teacher learners to get high marks in reading comprehension questions.

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